

Visit to the Biblioteca Nacional del Peru

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This February, after a long run of 5-day weeks and 4-week months at work, I was able to take a whole month off! So I was delighted to be able to spend my February in Peru, where I worked as a volunteer, teaching and getting to know a large group of children in a shanty town outside Lima. This was an incredible experience in many ways, which only further fuelled my ambition to work as a librarian with Voluntary Service Overseas (VSO) in the future. However, this article is not about volunteering! Just before leaving Peru I took the opportunity to visit its national library (the Biblioteca Nacional del Peru), which sits in the heart of the colonial centre of Lima. When I arrived, I was lucky to be offered a personal tour by one of the librarians there.

I learned that the Biblioteca Nacional was founded in 1821, immediately after Peru won its independence from Spain. It gradually built up a large collection including important ephemera. However in 1943 it suffered a devastating fire, the cause of which is not known. To rebuild the library's collections and at the same time raise its profile, a famous historian and librarian called Jorge Basadre was installed as Director. Basadre is now credited with having saved the library and given it the strong vision that it still has today. He is indeed much revered as the 'father' of Peruvian libraries, and when I entered the library, the first thing I saw was a large exhibition devoted to him and his life.

The second thing that struck me was that any Peruvian is entitled to join the national library and use its reading rooms. The reason for this is that Peru lacks a proper network of public libraries, so the Biblioteca attempts to provide for everybody by serving as both a national library *and* a public library. I had an image of the squeeze at the British Library if all 58 million of us were allowed to join! But the Biblioteca Nacional receives manageable numbers (around 2500 visitors per day during term-time, and anything between 200 and 2000 in the holidays), presumably because a large proportion of Peruvians live below the poverty line, with few educational opportunities and very limited transport.

However, on walking around I noticed many similarities to our national library, as well as differences. The Biblioteca has ten reading rooms that cover various subject areas including Research and Special Collections, but some that serve more unexpected functions. One, for example, is a large and colourful children's library and another is a school library, intended to provide for Peruvian pupils whose schools do not have such facilities.

Similarly to the British Library, the Biblioteca uses a purpose-built automated library system and has a room full of OPACs that users can search to find the room and shelfmark of an item. There is a major project underway to convert the card catalogues as well – some things are the same all over the world! Another familiar issue was that of space constraints. The Biblioteca Nacional is the legal deposit library for Peru (it publishes the national bibliography), and it is running out of space. Only the most current and useful stock is kept in the reading rooms, and the rest has to be requested from a large store that is on the same site. The materials are more exposed to risk than at the British Library however, as most of the store is above ground. However, these problems are going to be addressed in a brand new building which is now being planned.

The Biblioteca seems to be making a laudable effort to improve access to information for Peruvians with limited opportunities. Indeed, its vision statement explains that one of its aims is to lead the development of a national library system that will contribute to the social, cultural and economic development of the whole country. My guide told me that the library regularly donates books to the provinces, and it is also now building a series of 'model libraries' in previously information-starved communities.

On the whole, although I was only there for a short time I was extremely impressed by the wide variety of achievements that the Biblioteca Nacional del Peru is making in difficult circumstances, and I was constantly aware of a very strong sense of pride in the library, in both the staff and the readers.

Biblioteca Nacional del Peru: <http://www.binape.gob.pe/>

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